

Huamachuco Religion

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The Huamachuco area, located in the Peruvian Northern Highlands at about 3,000 meters above sea level, was approximately occupied since the Initial Period (2000 – 1000 BCE) by people practicing both camelid herding and mixed farming (e.g. tubers, maize, fruits, etc...). The dispersed households of the Colpa phase (until 900 BCE) were followed by a three-tier settlement system during the Sausagocha phase (900-200 BCE). Even though some sites may have featured special structures with a ceremonial function, this area was not influenced by the pan Andean Chavín cult. The following Purpucala phase (200 BCE – 300 CE) may have been marked by a population increase, the possible emergence of elites, and an increase in warfare and interaction with the Cajamarca area and the Callejón de Huaylas. The first examples of monumental architecture (residential structures called circular galleries) also appeared during this phase. People kept growing and large, monumental sites spread during the later Early Huamachuco phase (300 – 600 CE), including the well-known ceremonial site of Marcahuamachuco. Sites with monumental architecture were close to each other, had different functions, and were likely part of the same settlement system. The complex composed of Cerro Sazón and Cerro Tuscan may have been the political core of the settlement system. In the Amaru phase (600 – ca. 800 CE) the area was briefly influenced by the Wari state (Peruvian Central Highlands), especially at the shrine of Cerro Amaru, with no major impact on the settlement patterns. The unfinished site of Viracochapampa may represent an attempt by Cerro Sazón/Tuscan elites to replace Marcahuamachuco as the main ceremonial center in the area. However, in the Late Huamachuco phase (ca. 800 – 1000 CE) the importance of Cerro Sazón/Tuscan decreased, the monumentality of Marcahuamachuco kept growing, and the importance of the site reached its peak. During the Tuscan phase (1000 – 1470 CE), monumental construction stopped at Marcahuamachuco and two site clusters emerged, each one likely representing an independent polity. The Santa Barbara phase (1470 – 1532 CE) encompasses the Inka domination of Huamachuco, a time marked by profound social, political, and economic changes in this area. The modern town covers the Inka administrative center, and storage rooms ('qollqa') surrounded the settlement. While no written accounts are available about the sociopolitical organization and religious practices of the Huamachuco people, archaeological investigations and colonial documents provide us valuable information, especially about the late prehispanic phases. Niched halls, which were found at various sites including Marcahuamachuco and Viracochapampa, were key ceremonial buildings. These structures were roofed rectangular structures featuring niches along the walls and were built since the Early Huamachuco phase. Bones of ancestors were placed in the niches, and lineage-based feasts were celebrated in these buildings. Such celebrations highlighted the autonomy of the communities living in the area, and an ideology centered around the unity of community members eventually prevailed over the idea of an elite-dominated society expressed by the rich mausoleum (300 - 600 CE) found at the pilgrimage center of Cerro Amaru. The document (Relación) written by the Augustinian friars residing in Huamachuco around 1560 has shed light on myths, deities, rituals, and places considered sacred ('wak'as') by Huamachuco people, leading archaeologists to identify what was deemed the ancestral place of origin of this group (Cerro Huacate) and the oracular sanctuary (Cerro Icchal) dedicated to Catequil, the principal deity of Huamachuco.

Date Range: 300 CE - 1532 CE

Region: Huamachuco and surrounding territory

Region tags: Peru

Territory covered by the Province of Huamachuco during the Santa Barbara phase (1470-1532 CE, Inka

domination)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

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California Publications in American Archaeology and Ethnology. Vol 3, n. 4. Berkeley, California, pp. 223-399.

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Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 Description: No online sources are currently available

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 Description: No online textual corpora are currently available

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: The presence of Chimú (ca. 900 - 1470 CE) ceramics in the southeastern part of the territory (Carabamba Plateau: see Haley 1979 and Sghinolfi 2021) and pre-spun wool yarn found at Chan Chan, the capital of the Chimú empire, indicate contacts with coastal people. We do not know to what extent such contacts involved religion.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

- No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Field doesn't know

Notes: We know that the main god of the Huamachuco people, Catequil, was particularly revered by the Inka emperor Wayna Qhapaq (who ruled between 1493 and 1525: see Rowe 1946, 203), who also spread the cult to Ecuador. This emperor may have had a special relationship with this oracular deity and more broadly with Huamachuco, since he also revered another important 'wak'a' (sacred place/powerful place/supernatural being, see Bray 2015 for a thorough analysis of the term) of Huamachuco called Casiapoma/Casipoma and he also donated a 'wak'a' called Magacti/magachi (perhaps the water shrine of Cerro Amaru), which was providing people with water (see Rodriguez Rea 1992, 23,26; Topic 1992; Topic et al 2002, 311).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: During the Santa Barbara phase (1470-532 CE), the messenger of Catequil (who asked questions and received answers from the principal god of the Huamachuco people at the oracular shrine located on Cerro Icchal) may have been considered as a high priest (see Topic, Lange Topic and Melly Cava 2002: 312).

Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

Notes: The Relación written by the Augustinian friars around 1560 mentions the existence of a

high priest of Catequil ("sazerdote mayor": Rodriguez Rea, 1992, 20, 7r/7v). The text also mentions the name of a high priest, Xulcamango (Rodriguez Rea, 1992, 14, 4v/5r), so there may have been a hierarchy among priests. Not only Catequil had its own priest but also other deities that were worshipped by Huamachuco people had their own clerks (see, for example, Rodriguez Rea 1992, 28, 10r/10v).

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Field doesn't know

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 2

Notes: High priest/s Clerks

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: The high priest of Catequil was able to speak (question and interpret the answers) of the main deities (see, for example, the Inka emperor Atawallpa and the response he got from this oracle; Topic et al 2002, 305). The *Relación* written by the Augustinian friars around 1560 also mentions that priests were able to make people bleed without using needles and were able to do other things that were taught to them by divine creatures (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 14, 4v/5r).

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– No

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– No

↳ Powers are inherited:

– No

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: The Relación suggests that powers were transmitted by supernatural beings (4v/5r).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– No

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– No

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

Notes: While we do not know how leaders were chosen, the Relación written by the Augustinian friars around 1560 tells us how priests were selected (4v/5r). Deities attracted men that were particularly curious to a lagoon. The water of the lagoon dazed the chosen men and the deities brought them to a sacred place ('wak'a'). The chosen men were kept there for 5/10 days, during which they were taught their duties as priests. After that, the chosen men fasted and practiced sexual abstinence for 5 days. Next, they were ready to be priests (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 13-14).

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to the lack of written sources, it is hard to discern whether a building was strictly religious, residential or political. Therefore it is not easy to estimate what percentage of area was taken up by religious monuments.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 2500

Notes: Approximate size of El Castillo, Marcahuamachuco (see McCown 1945, 235-237 and

figures 6 and 9).

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we do not know the exact height of El Castillo, which likely was the core of Marcahuamachuco, John Topic (2009, 221-222) hypothesizes that it may have had 5 stories. Most of the building is now filled with rubble, to a depth of 9 meters.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Marcahuamacho (300 - 1470 CE), the largest site of the region and one of the religious cores of this area, featured different types of burials: - 'chullpa'-like towers (above-ground tombs/burial houses. See Isbell 1997 for a thorough discussion about these structures). - re-enterrable tombs - niches along the walls of niched halls The first two may have been temporary burials where human remains of important members of the society were placed until natural decomposition allowed to gather de-fleshed bones, which were subsequently placed in niches. As mentioned in the description of this religious group, niched halls were structures where lineage-based gatherings/feastings (involving the remains of lineage members) were taking place (Topic 2009). A multichambered funerary structure was found at Cerro Amaru (300 - 1000 CE). Grave goods were also recovered (metal, obsidian, textiles, Spondylus shells, human figurines, and ceramics). Ceramics show decorations that can be attributed to the Wari state (Peruvian Northern Central Highlands) and the Cajamarca polity (north of Huamachuco). These may represent the involvement of eminent Huamachuco figures in interregional trade networks (Lange Topic and Topic 2010, 202-204).

↳ Cemeteries:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: At the site of Namanchugo, at the foot of Cerro Icchal, Huamachuco people dedicated an oracular sanctuary/temple to their principal deity, Catequil (Cerro Icchal itself represented Catequil, while the outcrops next to it represented his brother Piguerao and his mother Cautaguan). Feasting activities started during the Early Intermediate Period (200 BCE - 600 CE) and the area was remodeled around 1200 CE. A U/C shaped mound was built and it recreated the shape of Cerro Icchal and its 3 peaks. The core of the temple was a small chamber that may have hosted the idol of Catequil (broken by the Inka emperor Atawallpa and later destroyed by the Augustinian friars: see Topic et al 2002, 312) and one person, that was likely listening and interpreting Catequil's will. An adjacent patio could have hosted up to a dozen people, perhaps elite pilgrims (Topic 2015). The Relación also mentions what may have been a temple dedicated to another supernatural being, Uzorpillao. The temple and other structures attached to it were destroyed by the friars (Rodríguez Rea 1992, 28). John Topic (1992, 71) argues that this temple may have been located on Cerro Urpillao in the upper Moche Valley. However, the archaeological remains found around the abovementioned mountain date to 300 - 600 CE rather than to late prehispanic times. Other small structures may have been dedicated to other supernatural beings, such as Cauri and Caoquilca (Rodríguez Rea, 22-23).

↳ Altars:

– No

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the section about temples, the sanctuary of Catequil may have featured an idol in its core structure. The sanctuary also featured a statue of Cautaguan/Mama Catequil, which is still preserved at the bottom of Cerro Icchal (Topic 2015). Some of the 'wak'as' (sacred places) worshiped by Huamachuco people were stones, wooden poles or other natural features/objects that had a unique shape (Rodríguez Rea 1992, p. 15).

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: As noted by Theodore McCown (1945, 237, 267-273, fig. 6, fig.13) and John and Theresa Topic (2000; 2009) major sites like Marcahuamachuco and Viracochapampa featured a Great Plaza and a central plaza, respectively, and smaller plazas. Nched halls were also key meeting places where members of a group (these groups were called pachacas by John and Theresa Topic, 2000, 187-188) that descended from the same mythical or real founder gathered to feast and venerate their ancestors, whose bones were located in niches built along the inner walls of the hall. Such structures have been identified at Marcahuamachuco, Viracochapampa and Cerro Sazón (Topic 2009) and they were associated to other structures called galleries, which featured remains indicating domestic activities. This suggests that they hosted people that attended the abovementioned gatherings. At Marcahuamachuco, such gatherings likely occurred only during the rainy austral summer, since no water source has been identified at the site (Topic and Lange Topic 2000, 191).

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: In 1988, John and Theresa Topic found a carved stone dating to the Early Intermediate Period (200 BCE - 600 CE)/Middle Horizon (600 - 1000 CE) in Marcahuamachuco representing two parrots flanking an unidentified figure. They hypothesize that it may represent one of the minor supernatural beings/'wak'as' of Huamachuco, Paucar (Rodriguez Rea, 1992, 30; Topic 1992, 83-89).

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: At the bottom of Cerro Icchal, there is a carved stone that may have been part of the sanctuary dedicated to Catequil. This stone likely represents Catequil's mother, Mama Catequil/Cautaguan. The carved stone is 185 cm tall (plus 15 cm buried in the ground). The head, limbs and a cavity in the abdominal area are clearly visible (Topic 2015, fig. 12.5).

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Notes: Tenon heads were also found at Marcahuamachuco and nearby sites (see McCown 1945, plates 16 and 17), but we do not know if such anthropomorphic figures represent supernatural beings or ancestors. As suggested by Topic et al (2002, 314) such heads may date to the Early Intermediate Period (200 BCE - 600 CE) or the Middle Horizon (600 - 1000 CE). Tenon heads were also found at Chuquicanra, a site close to Catequil's sanctuary at Cerro Icchal (Topic 2015, 374).

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: McCown (1945, plates 16 and 17) reported other carved stones with stylized symbols, but we do not know if these had a religious meaning.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Marcahuamacho was likely one of the most important ceremonial centers of the region, and ritual activities (especially the veneration of ancestors) were carried out at the site. The occupation of this center may have been seasonal (austral summer, from December to March) rather than permanent due to the lack of water sources on the plateau that hosted the site (Topic 2009, 220). As mentioned by the *Relación* written by the Augustinian friars in 1560 (Rodríguez Rea 1992), idols were also located in caves and people left offerings to minor supernatural beings in such places. The site of Cerro Amaru likely played an important role during the Early Intermediate Period and the Middle Horizon, and rituals connected to water and fertility may have been carried out at this site (Topic and Lange Topic 1992). As mentioned in the section about temples, the oracular site of Namanchugo, near Cerro Icchal, hosted the temple of Catequil, the principal deity of Huamachuco (Topic 2015).

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Natural features played an important role in Pre-Columbian Andean religions (see, for example Salomon and Urioste 1991; Bray 2015). As mentioned in the previous sections, Cerro Icchal and its three peaks may have represented Carequil, his brother, and his mother (Topic 2015). The shrine of Cerro Amaru may have been built in area where the water table was particularly close to the ground (Topic and Lange Topic 1992). Supernatural beings were also worshipped in natural features like caves (Rodríguez Rea 1992; Topic 1992). Standing stones ('huancas') were also worshipped (Topic 1992, 82).

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: During the Early Intermediate Period (200 BCE - 600 CE) and Middle Horizon (600 - 1000 CE), the site of Cerro Amaru may have been a water shrine and a pilgrimage site, attracting pilgrims from various areas of the Andean region, as indicated by the presence of exotic pottery coming from Cajamarca, the Wari state and the Peruvian Central Coast (Topic and Lange Topic 1992). Later, during the Late Intermediate Period (1000 - 1470 CE), the oracular site of Namanchuco, near Cerro Icchal, became a pilgrimage destination. However, in this case pilgrims likely lived within a radius of 20 km from the sanctuary and may have stayed at the site of Chulite while visiting Namanchugo (Topic 2015, 375-376).

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Field doesn't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Cremation:

– Field doesn't know

Mummification:

– No

Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: De-fleshed bones placed in niched halls - badly preserved human bones in Cerro Amaru mausoleum

Notes: Bones of ancestors/kin group members were first de-fleshed (either by people or by natural decomposition) and placed in re-enterable tombs before being placed in niches located along the walls of niched halls (Lange Topic and Topic 2010, 192- 193; Topic 2009, 222-223). At the mausoleum excavated by John and Theresa Topic at Cerro Amaru, human bones were not very well preserved. Two individuals were placed on a bed of Spondylus shells (harvested in Ecuador and usually offered to deities connected to water), but it is not clear in what position (Topic and Lange Topic 1992, 172).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The bodies of deceased that were later placed in niches located along the walls of niched halls may have naturally decomposed (Topic 2009, 222).

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned in the Internment section, bones of ancestral figures/kin members may have been first placed in re-enterable tombs and then in niches (Topic 2009, 222-223).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :
 - No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: The mausoleum found at Cerro Amaru (Middle Horizon, 600 - 1000 CE) may have included burials of retainers (Topic and Lange Topic 1992, 172).

Are grave goods present:

- Yes

- ↳ Personal effects:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Valuable items:
 - Yes

Notes: While very few or no grave goods were found at Marcahuamachuco, the mausoleum at Cerro Amaru (Middle Horizon, 600 - 1000 CE) featured sumptuary goods (Topic and Lange Topic 1992; Lange Topic and Topic 2000; Topic 2009).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 600 CE - 1000 CE

- ↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):
 - Yes

Notes: Gold and silver tipped gloves, copper and bronze 'tupu' pin (Topic and Lange Topic 1992, 172; Lange Topic and Topic 2000, 202).

- ↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):
 - Yes

Notes: Spondylus shells, textiles, obsidian, a possible pyrite mirror (Lange Topic and Topic 2000, 202).

- ↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:
 - Yes [specify]: Decorated pottery

Notes: Decorated pots from Cajamarca, Peruvian Central Coast and the Wari state (Peruvian Central Highlands) (Lange Topic and Topic 2000, 202).

- ↳ Other grave goods:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is not clear if the elites buried in the mausoleum found at Cerro Amaru (Middle Horizon, 600 - 1000 CE) were members of the same family/related (Topic and Lange Topic 1992; Lange Topic and Topic 2000).

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Niched halls

Notes: see Topic 2009

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god, which created all existing things and beings (including other deities and humans), was called Ataguju and was believed to live in the sky (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 10). However, it should be reminded that the principal and more revered 'wak'a'/supernatural being/entity was Catequil, who was related to Ataguju (born from the relationship between one of Ataguju's "sons", Guamansuri, and a human being, Cautaguan) (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 17-18; Topic et al 2002, 304).

- ↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):
 - No
- ↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: Even though we do not have much information about how much the supreme god Ataguju knew about the mortal world, it can be hypothesized that the supreme god knew what was happening. As mentioned above, Ataguju created everything. Moreover, the Augustinian friars reported that the god was also governing everything from the sky (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 10).

- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Ataguju created all existing things and beings. Moreover, he was worshipped by

Huamachuco people and believed to bestow them a long life (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 10-12).

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Augustinian friars mentioned that priests and people carried out sacrifices while worshipping Ataguju. Guinea pigs and camelids were killed and a pole was greased with the blood of such animals. People and priests also prepared and offered maize beer ('chicha') to Ataguju and to all other supernatural beings. Coca leaves were also burned and their smoke was believed to reach Ataguju in the sky (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 10-12; Topic 1992).

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Yes

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– No

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: While it is not clear if the Augustinian friars talk about Ataguju, people that were chosen to become priests they were attracted to body of water and then "dazed" by the supernatural being (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 13-14).

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Archaeologists John and Theresa Topic have suggested that ancestors were revered at structures called niched halls, which were found at major centers like Marcahuamachuco, Viracochapampa and other sites located in the Huamachuco area (Topic 2009).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Among other things, natural features, objects, and animals may have also been considered 'wak'as' (thus sacred entities). Some of the 'wak'as' revered by Huamachuco people were, for example, stone idols (Llaiguen, Guachecoal, and Caoquilca), wooden idols (Casiapoma), peaks (Yamaguanca and Yamoguanca), jars (Magachi/Magacti), foxes, planets, satellites and constellations (see Rodriguez Rea 1992; Topic 1992).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: 'Wak'as' were revered by Huamachuco people in the hope of: - a long and healthy life (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 12); - water (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 22-23, 26); - coming out as winners during wars (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 23, 25); - high quality dye for textiles (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 25); - becoming rich (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 31); - keeping their flock safe (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 32); - a good harvest (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 34).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Augustinian friars mentioned that Huamachuco people were scared of their principal deity, Catequil (associated with thunders and lightning) (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 18). Moreover, the 'wak'a' called Uzopillao may have punished and killed people that attempted to reach it (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 28).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While documents do not clearly talk about 'waka's' hunger, Huamachuco people were definitely making offerings (objects, food, sacrifices of animals) to supernatural beings in the hope of obtaining rewards (see Rodriguez Rea 1992; Topic et al 2002, 323-324).

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: Catequil was born from the union of a mortal woman (Cautaguan) and a divine creature (Guamansuri). Guamansuri, created by Ataguju, was sent to Huamachuco, which was inhabited by people called guachemines. Guamansuri worked for the guachemines and eventually seduced and impregnated a guachemin woman, Cautaguan. When the guachemines found that out, they killed and burned Guamansuri. Cautaguan gave birth to two eggs and then died. Catequil and Piguerao came into the world. Catequil resuscitated his mother and received Guamansuri's slings from her. The weapons were used to kill/drive away the guachemines. Catequil eventually talked with Ataguju and asked him to repopulate Huamachuco. The supreme god sent Catequil to Cerro Huacate (located along the Santa River) and dug out Huamachuco people of the ground (Topic 1998, 112).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The Augustinian friars argued that, when revered at his sanctuary located in Porcón (Namanchugo/Cerro Icchal), Catequil was giving people what they needed, including food, camelids and sons/daughters (Rodríguez Rea 1992, 19).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: While we do not know if people perceived some events as Catequil's punishments, the Augustinian friars mentioned that Huamachuco people were scared of their principal deity (Rodríguez Rea 1992, 18).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: Also in this case, the Augustinian friars do not talk about Catequil's hunger, but we know that people made offerings to their principal deity (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 19). This was also confirmed by excavations conducted at the sanctuary of Namanchugo/Cerro Icchal, where John and Theresa Topic found potsherds, Spondylus shells and river-rolled stones. The latter may be related to Catequil's weapon, the sling (Topic et al 2002).

↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:
– Field doesn't know

↳ In trance possession:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– Yes

Notes: A priest questioned the oracular 'wak'a' and then Catequil's answer was announced (Topic et al 2002, 305). John and Theresa Topic (2002, 321-323) argued that the response may have been announced to a restricted number of people through the flow of liquids in an oracular canal, which was split into a northern and a southern side. Liquids running evenly on both sides may have indicated a positive response.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Notes: Some of the 'wak'as' worshipped by Huamachuco people were related. Ataguju, the creator, gave "birth" to Guamansuri. The latter had a relationship with a mortal being (who was also revered by Huamachuco people), Cautaguan. The latter gave birth to Piguerao and Catequil, the principal deity of Huamachuco (see Rodriguez Rea 1992; Topic 1998).

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Notes: While Ataguju was the supreme creator, at least during late Prehispanic times, Catequil was considered the principal deity of Huamachuco people (Topic 1998; Topic 2015). The Augustinian friars also stated that during the Inka domination there were 9 principal 'wak'as' (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 21; Topic 1992, 67) and various minor 'wak'as' (Topic 1992, 76). John Topic (1992; 1998) argued that at least some of them were related to the four Indigenous 'guarangas' (administrative units composed of 1000 people) into which the Inka structured the province of Huamachuco.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 300 BCE - 1532 CE

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

Notes: The Relación written by the Augustinian friars tells us that Catequil was related to thunders and perhaps to water (Rodriguez Rea 1992; Topic 2015, 383). Other supernatural beings like Llauiguen, Caoquilca, and Magacti/Magachi were related to water, while others were related to war (Rodriguez Rea 1992), fertility (Rodriguez Rea

1992, 41; Topic 1992, 82), and textiles (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 25).

- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

- Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: While we do not know if people perceived some events as Catequil's punishments, the Augustinian friars mentioned that Huamachuco people were scared of their principal deity (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 18).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

- Yes

- ↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done only by high god:
 - No

- ↳ Done by many supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:
 - No

- ↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:
 - Yes

- ↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– No

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:
– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

Notes: Good dyeing for textiles (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 25).

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

↳ Monogamy (males):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Monogamy (females):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: According to the Augustinian friars, male sexual abstinence was carried out in various occasions, such as: - for five days, when a man was selected to become a priest (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 13-14); - during the three days that preceded animal sacrifices, priests had to practice sexual abstinence (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 16).

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting was practiced, for example: - for five days, when a man was selected to become a priest (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 13-14); - during the three days that preceded animal sacrifices, priests had to fast (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 16); - the priests of the 'wak'a' called Quispeguayanay (which was rewarding people with good dyeing for clothes) fasted when required (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 25); - the priests of Magacti/Magachi fasted for two days when requesting water to this 'wak'a' (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 26); - for five days, when twins were born (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 29); - during eclipses (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 33).

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on

desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Notes: Even though it was not a requirement, textiles, pots, animals, and Spondylus shells were voluntarily offered to supernatural beings (Rodriguez Rea 1992; Topic et al 2002).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: The participation in kin-based meetings at sites like Marcahuamachuco and Viracochapampa.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: The Augustinian friars stated that Huamachuco people had idols in their own houses and they compared them to Roman lares and penates. Such deities provided people with numerous and healthy guinea pigs and camelids, chili peppers, good maize beer, heat during the cold season, among other things (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 39-41).

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 300

Notes: John and Theresa Topic (2000, 188, 191 - Boletín de Arqueología PUCP) argued that galleries located next to niched halls at Marcahuamachuco likely hosted 200-300 people. This may have been the number of people that participated in these lineage-based celebrations.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized

way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Field doesn't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: John Topic (2009) hypothesized that Huamachuco people were organized into community-oriented chiefdoms. Such groups may have featured a cultural unity and used Marcahuamachuco as a ceremonial center for lineage-based gatherings. The mausoleum found at Cerro Amaru may have represented a failed attempt to create an individualizing chiefdom during the Middle Horizon (600 - 1000 CE). During the Inka domination, Huamachuco became an administrative center and the core of the province of Huamachuco. The province was subdivided into seven 'guaranga's (administrative units composed of 1000 households); four were composed by Indigenous people, one by coastal people resettled ('mitmaq') in Huamachuco, one by highland people resettled in this area, and one by inhabitants of the 'chaupiyunga' zone (500-2300 meters above sea level) (Topic 1998).

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Field doesn't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Field doesn't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The adherent of this religion became part of the Inka empire during the Santa Barbara phase (1470 - 1532 CE) and were subdivided into 'guarangas', as mentioned in the Levels of Social Complexity section (Topic 1998; 2009).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1470 CE - 1532 CE

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: Two round storage structures ('qollqa') dated between the Early Intermediate Period (200 BCE - 600 CE) and the Middle Horizon (600 - 1000 CE) were found at Cerro Amaru and they were used to store maize, perhaps used during feasting activities carried out at the water shrine (Topic and Chiswell 1992, 226-229; Topic and Topic 1992, 172).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: During the Santa Barbara phase (1470 - 1532 CE)/Inka domination, the Inka empire built storage rooms ('qollqa'). Five groups of storage rooms were identified on three hills surrounding the town of Huamachuco and they were likely used to store tubers and grains (Topic and Chiswell 1993).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1470 CE - 1532 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: As stated by John and Theresa Topic (1993), roads existed before the Inka domination. However, the Inka empire likely expanded the road system and built stations ('tampu') along it.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in

question:

– Yes

Notes: When the Huamachuco area became part of the Inka empire, heads of household likely had to offer labor service ('mit'a') to the empire (see D'Altroy 2015, 395-401). The Augustinian friars also talk about tribute that weavers had to pay, likely to the Inka empire (Rodriguez Rea 1992, 25).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1470 CE - 1532 CE

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: During the Inka domination, Huamachuco people were likely under the control of Inka provincial inspectors ('tokoyrikoq') (see D'Altroy 2015, 358).

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1470 CE - 1532 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It can be hypothesized that during the Santa Barbara phase Huamachuco people first supported and then were integrated into the Inka army. During the conquest of Northern Peru (about 1470 CE), Huamachuco people may have been allied with the Inka, since we know that the Inka army walked through Huamachuco unhindered (Rowe 1948, 44) and that the emperor Wayna Qhapaq had a close relation with the Catequil oracle (Topic et al 2002). Moreover, the Inka assigned the 'chaupiyungas' (intermediate zones located between 500 and 2,300 meters above sea level) to Huamachuco (Netherly 1977, 314) and this may have been a way to reward Huamachuco's support.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1470 CE - 1532 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Augustinian friars mentioned that the sanctuary of Catequil located near Cerro Icchal owned several estates ('haciendas'), servants and flocks. Such wealth was likely used to sustain the priests and make offerings to Catequil, rather than being used to sustain all the adherents to this religion (Topic 2015, 373-374).

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)